

Research question:

How do modern internet-based social media affect adolescent emotional and social development?

Introduction

In 2023, the Seattle public school district issued an unprecedented lawsuit against the social media companies - Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, Snapchat, and TikTok - accusing them of creating conditions triggering a youth mental health crisis. Teachers with concern had observed exhausted and socially withdrawn students incorporated into the online world until they finally decided to take serious steps. “Defendants have successfully exploited the vulnerable brains of youth, hooking tens of millions of students across the country into positive feedback loops of excessive use and abuse of Defendants’ social media platforms” - stated the lawsuit. Plaintiffs had demanded changes in platforms’ way of working and compensation for mental-health help the school had to provide (Johnson). For the first time a society stood up against Silicon Valley, presenting social media as a harmful force tarnishing adolescent emotional and social development.

We are immersed in Internet and social media content on a daily basis - the endless flow of notifications, messages, and updates; social pressure; and the need to appear “normal.” It has become impossible to live without using or appearing in cyberspace. A survey from 2025 shows that over 5.2 billion people use the Internet daily, and most of them are active on social media, spending an average of 2.5 hours per day online (Kemp). The most popular platforms are YouTube, Facebook, and Pinterest, while the most active group consists of participants aged 16-24 (Sheikh). These statistics underscore the omnipresent influence of the Internet contest and encourage reflection about its damaging effects.

“Common sense is the collection of prejudices acquired by age eighteen” - these words by Lincoln Barnett describe the importance of adolescence. According to the WHO, adolescence is the period from 10 to 19 years old (WHO). Medical research proves that the human body fundamentally develops in our early childhood and matures up into the mid-to-late 20s. One of the most profound measures of the so-called “maturity” of an individual lies in their emotional and social competences. They allow us to interpret and care about our well-being, as well as people around us. Scientists emphasize that these traits are strictly connected to brain (frontal lobes and amygdala) maturation and develop from puberty (11-13) until late adolescence (20s) (Johnson et al.). During that time we learn self-regulating behavior, situational judgment, resilience, and rational reasoning. Research in neurobiology and psychology shows that emotional and social development serve as a fundament for the formation of empathy, decision-making, and identity, becoming one of the most important attributes individuals must preserve.

We are what we eat. We do what we are taught. And we shape our worldview based on experiences and surrounding content. In the modern Internet and social media-based age, what are we surrounding ourselves with? What content do we see, and how does it shape us?

Main body

Pew's 2024 survey reveals that adolescents spend approx. 4-5 hours per day on social media. Many of them report they use the Internet to feel connected to friends (74%), showcase creativity (63%), or find support and acceptance (52% each). On the contrary, participants also revealed that social media causes them to feel overwhelmed (39%), excluded (31%), or pressured (29%). Above that, 48% say social media has a generally negative impact on their peers, and 60% of them reported they believe they have little or no control over data collected by Internet companies (Rothwell).

Presented trends are commonly reported by various other surveys, such as Marciano et al.'s meta-analysis, whose results disclose a positive association between time spent on social media and decreased well-being (Marciano et al.).

The above data encourages the conclusion that social media generally has a negative impact on adolescents' mental health - contributing to anxiety, stress, and lower self-esteem. Despite that, it has to be taken into account that correlations do not imply causation - and exclusions always occur. After all - like everything else - the Internet and social media are just tools. While they are designed with a specific goal and effects, their impact ultimately depends on the way they are used. Used wisely - e.g. for communication, showcasing skills, and sharing joyous moments, it can have a positive impact on one's development, mental health, and social life.

As mentioned previously, the period of adolescence shapes our body, as well as traits and abilities. Firstly, it is a time of important changes in the structure and function of the brain - regions associated with emotion, social signalling, rewards, and punishments (amygdala, medial prefrontal cortex) become more responsive than ones responsible for regulation and self-control (ventrolateral and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex). Above that, our brain undergoes continuous processes of synaptic pruning, creating new neuronal pathways - new habits, patterns of behavior, and values. This - among others - can result in stereotypical teenage behaviors, such as increased emotional reactivity, sensitivity, decreased impulse control, or problems with self-control (Guyer et al.).

Moreover, the period of adolescence is characterized by a change of perspective and value system. Children expand freedom and learn independent thinking. Altogether the mentioned processes often result in rebellion against taught values and a shift in worldview. Social life and peer relationships become central to adolescents' lives, which can have both positive and negative consequences. They impact adolescents' way of thinking by encouraging novelty and applying pressure through many behaviors: exclusion, humiliation, and negative or positive feedback - be it in real life or on the Internet. In the most vulnerable period - time of forming identity - social position and experiences greatly influence behavior, even leading to mimicking negative behaviors just to feel accepted and understood.

After underscoring the importance and characteristics of adolescence, we can proceed, and further explore how and why technology can impact teenagers in a harmful way.

Firstly, technology influences our body. Prolonged screen exposure and improper posture leads to various pains, defects, and diseases. It is proven that use of technology - especially in unsuitable conditions - increases risk of ophthalmological, musculoskeletal, and cardiovascular problems, as well as metabolic disruptions. When they occur in the period of adolescence, they can trigger damage for an entire life - not only biological, but also emotional (e.g., decreased self-image, exclusion from social groups).

Investigating deeper, the cross-sectional study of Scott et al. on over 11,000 UK adolescents (age 13-15) displayed the association between heavier daily social media use and poorer sleep patterns (late sleep onset, trouble falling asleep) (Scott et al.). As it is known, sleep is one of the conditions of survival - a time of regeneration, transferring memories from the hippocampus to the brain cortex, and many others. For adolescents, it is even more important, as it creates a time and place for the brain to develop and regulate. Its degeneration can lead to a decrease in cognitive functions and emotional stability.

Still, the most potent effects of the Internet lie in its influence on the brain. Social media platforms are programmed to trigger reward centres - through the likes, comments, and shares. They activate a dopamine pathway and utilize variable reinforcement (in the form of notifications, updates, and “pop-ups”). Continuous posting and checking notifications constructs a self-reinforcing, habitable, positive feedback loop. In summary, they work like drugs - eventually when tolerance is built, the brain requires more intense social stimuli (more likes). This is supplemented by notifications (maintaining tension) and personalized content - phenomena like filter bubbles and echo chambers (keeping interest) (De et al.). The adolescents are an exceptionally susceptible group, with their developing limbic system and neural pathways. As the popular saying goes, “You can’t teach an old dog new tricks” - created during our development habits, pathways, and deformations have a continuous and profound effect on everything in our life. This means that adolescents should be particularly careful about their routine and repeated behaviors - including what they decide to see and do online.

Having laid the biological groundwork, the psychological and social consequences can be explained. Social media revolves around social groups and relationships. It creates a ground for comparison, which can lead to jealousy, low self-worth, and fear of missing out (FoMO). Encourages adapting traits and values to fit in online criteria—to be more liked and accepted—at the expense of uniqueness and authenticity. Diminishes natural emotional development. Moreover, it can inhibit or accelerate it by freely giving anyone access to dangerous (violence, pornography) or “brainrot” (sensational, meaningless) materials. And paradoxically, although the social media’s aim is to connect people, numerous studies report they trigger feelings of loneliness and social withdrawal, especially when used passively as a compensation (Bonsaksen and Ruffolo).

Social media is a tool, and its effect depends on the user. Every one of them is unique, formed by experiences, culture, and genes, which have a profound influence on how social media impacts us. For instance, users living in individualistic countries, focused on competition and status, will be more vulnerable to social media's negative effects than people from collective cultures, centered around community (Gordesli et al.). An individual raised in a traditional family with strict rules about the Internet is less likely to use social media in excess, even as an adult, than a child who had unrestricted access to technology. Thus, the extent of social media's influence must be approximated, taking into account individuals' environment, experiences, and values.

Lastly, I would like to point out that social media's dangers always existed in real life - social exclusion, humiliation, gossip, and similar. In the age of the Internet, they just mutate and intensify, occurring worldwide under the custody of algorithms.

So how can we protect ourselves? Given the present state of the Internet - the amount of negative or dangerous data - it is crucial to address this issue through innovative methods, at its root and in early stages. We can't delete the safety problem, nor stop the technological development - we can only deal with the consequences and try to prevent further harm. We can educate adolescents on how to use media in a safe and meaningful way - according to its primary goal. We could try to explain to them how their behavior impacts others. This can be archived - for instance - by integrating digital ethics, elements of neuroscience, or social psychology into school curricula. Next, we can require platforms to alter their algorithms and tighten regulations. And most importantly, we can encourage and provide support for the adolescents to create a safe and peaceful environment. It is crucial to remember that we still have the influence and power to change and improve the current situation.

Conclusion

“We become what we behold. We shape our tools, and thereafter our tools shape us.” (Marshall McLuhan). Concluding points explored in this essay, omnipotent modern Internet-based social media have altered our reality - modified old and created new threads. Although these platforms are designed for the benefit of humanity, improper and excessive use can cause serious harm on every plane. Their impact on adolescents’ development is systematic - rooted in biological and sociocultural influences on an organism in its developing and most vulnerable stages. They redesign biological processes, the structure of the brain, values, and beliefs, which results in destruction of one’s identity and depersonalization. To prevent that, parents, schools, institutions, and technologists must collaborate to educate adolescents and teach them to consciously shape safe Internet space. It’s up to us to change the current situation — we must choose to act, and we must do so now, when we still have resources and influence. According to President John F. Kennedy, “We can say with some assurance that, although children may be the victims of fate, they will not be the victims of our neglect.” (John F. Kennedy). In the modern age, as social media becomes the biggest threat for the safety and development of adolescents - can we still sign under those words?

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